

Experimental Analysis of Channel Frequency-, Space- and Object- Consistency at the W-band

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Abstract—Sub-terahertz (sub-THz) frequencies provide huge untapped bandwidth for high data rates in wireless communications and high-precision sensing applications. Understanding radio channel characteristics at sub-THz frequency bands is important to identify potential applications. This letter investigated the frequency dependence, spatial consistency and impact of blockage at the W-band. Employing the vector-network-analyzer (VNA) based virtual antenna array (VAA) channel sounder, several wideband measurements covering three frequency bands, eight spatial locations, with or without the blockage at the W-band were performed. The experimental analysis demonstrated that channel characteristics have good frequency consistency and a strong correlation with the spatial environment. The above research is of great significance for achieving fast beam alignment and channel prediction in different spatial locations.

Index Terms—Channel sounding, sub-terahertz, virtual antenna array, spatial-temporal channel characteristic.

I. INTRODUCTION

SUB-terahertz (sub-THz) technology is envisioned as one of key technologies for 6G, providing huge untapped bandwidth [1]–[3]. Understanding of radio channel characteristics is important to identify potential applications, since many key wireless system design parameters, e.g. communication link distances, required antenna directivity and gain, multiplexing or beamforming schemes, etc. are determined by channels of the deployment scenario.

Understanding frequency dependence of channel parameters has been an important topic for research and standardization. It is currently difficult to determine which sub-THz frequency bands will be employed for future communication and sensing systems. Knowledge of differences and similarities of channel models across frequency bands can help decide which bands are preferable and how to best utilize similar channel properties at different bands. The existing works have been focused on frequency bands below the W-band [4]. In recent years, there has been strong interest to extend the existing channel models for above 100 GHz [5], [6]. In [7], measurement campaigns were carried out in indoor corridor at 100 and 300 GHz

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to measure the power-angle-delay profiles (PADP)s. In [8], [9], frequency dependence of large-scale channel parameters, e.g. path loss, shadowing, antenna misalignment is analysed for different sub-THz bands. The power angle spectra for different frequency bands were reported in [10]. Double directional channel measurements and its frequency dependence within the sub-THz bands were discussed in [5].

We need to understand to which extend dominant propagation paths over many spatial locations, with or without presence of objects spanning different frequency bands can be well predicted using few samples measurement/simulation in the space, frequency and object dimensions. Such concept is exploited to reduce the complexity for dynamic ray tracing simulation [11]. Moreover, it is of interest to know whether knowledge of simple environment and object geometry (e.g. map) can be used for helping analyze channel spatial and object consistency, e.g. in the METIS channel model [12].

The state-of-the-art work, however, is lacking in the analysis on the frequency dependent, spatial consistent and object dependent channel behaviors, especially in the W-band. Ray tracing (RT) simulation is a good alternative for collecting massive site-specific channel data when measurement data is inaccessible or too time-consuming to obtain. Preliminary work on RT simulation in the sub-THz band have shown promising results [13]. However, the RT simulation accuracy at the W-band is still immature, making it unsuitable for the consistency study at this stage. Compared with the existing literature, our work performed the indoor measurement in the W-band and investigated the channel consistence in the frequency, space and impact of object domains simultaneously based on the same set of measured data. Moreover, we employed the newly developed virtual array-based channel sounder at the W band [14] to achieve high spatial resolution and signal-to-noise ratio compared to the directional scanning scheme (DSS) scheme widely adopted in the literature. The main contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- By utilization of the newly developed channel sounder, wideband measurements covering three frequency bands at the W band, eight spatial locations were conducted, with and without the presence of the metallic plate. This measurement campaign allows us to investigate the frequency, spatial and object consistency.
- A beamforming algorithm [15] is employed for the ultra-wideband large-scale uniform circular array (UCA) based on directional antenna elements. Unlike state-of-art works where antennas exhibit different radiation patterns at different frequency bands, corrugated antenna of same antenna patterns at different bands are used, ensuring that

Fig. 1. Measurement scenario photo for the OLOS scenario. Note the metallic plate is removed in the LOS scenario.

antenna effects are properly taken into account.

- Channel parameters across different frequency bands, different spatial locations, with and without presence of blockage are analyzed.

II. MEASUREMENT SETUP

A. Measurement System

The newly developed W-band channel sounder based on VNA, which is capable of performing ultra-wideband, long-range, phase-coherent channel measurements is employed in the work [14]. The Rx antenna is a wideband vertically polarized omni-directional Biconical antenna (model number: SAO-7531140230-10-S1) with a bandwidth from 75 GHz to 110 GHz, and the Tx antenna is a vertically polarized corrugated horn antenna (model number: ASY-CWG-5-750) with the same operating frequency as the Rx antenna. The employed corrugated horn antenna is known for its consistent antenna pattern across frequency bands, which is essential to ensure that the variations of measured radio channels across frequency bands are solely introduced by the propagation channels, not by the antenna patterns. A virtual UCA at the Tx side is realized by rotating the corrugated antenna, with an offset 5cm to the rotation center and a rotation step of 0.5° , leading to a UCA with 720 antenna elements and $r = 5$ cm. At each virtual UCA element, three frequency bands (i.e. 75-76 GHz, 92-93 GHz and 109-110 GHz) were measured simultaneously with 1001 frequency sampling points set for each frequency band. Therefore, the bandwidth is set to 1 GHz, leading to a delay resolution of 1 ns and path length resolution of 30 cm. Furthermore, the longest detectable path is 300 m, which is sufficient for the indoor entrance scenario. The spacing between two adjacent antenna elements on the virtual UCA at 109-110 GHz is 0.04 cm, which is smaller than half wavelength at this band. This is essential to avoid the undesired spatial aliasing in the measurements. The height of both the Tx and Rx antennas is 0.985 m above the ground.

B. Measurement Scenario and Measurement Campaign

The measurements were performed in a rectangular entrance hall of 8.19×4.18 m² shown in Fig. 2. Most of the surrounding walls are made of concrete and two metallic radiators are

Fig. 2. Measurement scenario and trajectory based on estimated MPCs for the OLOS scenario at 75-76 GHz.

fixed on the wall. In addition, some wooden doors, a glass window, a glass door, a metallic elevator and two stairs are embedded in the surrounding walls. To investigate spatial consistency, the Rx was moved to eight different spatial locations at equal intervals of 0.5 m as shown in Fig. 2. The distance between the centered Rx4 and UCA center at the Tx side is 6.1 m. Meanwhile, two scenarios were considered in the measurement: line of sight (LOS) and Obstructed-LOS (OLOS) scenario by placing a metal plate of 0.75×0.75 m² between the Tx and Rx4, as shown in Fig. 1.

III. MULTIPATH EXTRACTION METHOD AND SIMILARITY EVALUATION MATRICES

A. Multipath Extraction Method

The method of VAA channel sounding based on directional antenna was applied in channel measurement [15]. Assume a UCA composed of P directional antenna elements and the angular position of the p th element is $\varphi_p = 2\pi \cdot (p-1)/P$. Assume all MPCs are confined to the azimuth plane and illuminate the UCA with plane wave. The channel characteristics of the k th path can be represented by incident angle ϕ_k , complex amplitude α_k and delay τ_k . The superimposed frequency response of the p th element to all K paths is

$$H_p(f) = \sum_{k=1}^K a_k \exp(-j2\pi f \tau_k) \cdot a_p(f, \phi_k) \quad (1)$$

where $a_p(f, \phi_k)$ is the array manifold coefficient of the p th element from the k th path [15]. The classical beamforming algorithm based on directional antenna is written as

$$Q(f, \phi) = \sum_{p=1}^P \omega_p(f, \phi) \cdot H_p(f) \quad (2)$$

where ω_p is the complex weight for the p th antenna element.

$$\omega_p = \frac{1}{\sqrt{P_0}} \exp \left[-\frac{j2\pi fr}{c} \cos(\phi - \varphi_p) \right] \cdot s(\phi) \quad (3)$$

where $s(\phi)$ is the windows function, and its optimal threshold width is usually 180° [15]. P_0 is total power for normalization.

The frequency response $Q(f, \phi)$ is obtained using beamforming algorithm, and the corresponding channel impulse response in delay-angular domain can be calculated by performing inverse Fourier transform on (2) and represented as

$$h'(\tau, \phi) = \sum_{f=f_L}^{f=f_U} Q(f, \phi) \cdot \exp(j2\pi f\tau) \quad (4)$$

B. PAS similarity

Note that single snapshot of the channel was recorded for each location and the focus is on channel spatial profile for beamforming operations. Therefore, popular metrics, e.g. correlation matrix distance (CMD) to characterize the channel consistency [16] and spatial consistency decorrelation distance used in 3GPP channel models to ensure decorrelated spatial channels were not employed here for data analysis.

In total, we have recorded $2 \times 8 \times 720 \times 3 \times 1001$ samples (i.e. 2 scenarios, 8 spatial locations, 720 virtual array elements, 3 frequency bands and 1001 frequency points). As a result, we have 48 two-dimensional PADPs to be analyzed and compared. For the similarity evaluation of the frequency and presence of object dimensions, the similarity of power-angular spectrum (PAS) [17] is used as a quantitative metric, with 1 and 0 denoting full similarity and total dissimilarity, respectively.

The PAS similarity metric is widely accepted in the literature and of critical importance of beamforming operations in the mmWave and sub-THz communications. The PAS can be obtained from the measured PADP by summing up the power in the delay domain. For similarity analysis for different frequency bands, the PAS similarity metric is calculated directly. For the measurements in the LOS and O-LOS scenarios, we need to properly take the LOS component into consideration when calculating similarity in presence of object: 1) For the spatial locations where the object does not block the LOS trajectory in the OLOS scenario, the PAS similarity metric is employed directly. 2) For the spatial locations where LOS trajectory is blocked in the OLOS scenario, we can also calculate the similarity with or without the LOS path (by removing the LOS path in the LOS scenario).

As for the spatial dimension, we are more interested in the path birth and death among different spatial locations rather than the natural path trajectory evolution over spatial locations. The similarity metric for the spatial dimension is more problematic, as the delay and azimuth of all MPCs would vary with the change of spatial positions. We will introduce a new fitting curve to analyze the spatial consistency.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULT

The PADP for LOS and OLOS scenarios at three frequency bands at Rx4 are shown in Fig. 3 as an example. Seven multipath components (MPC)s with highest power values

TABLE I
THE PAS SIMILARITY PERCENTAGE AT DIFFERENT SCENARIOS

Frequency	RX1	RX4 (removing LOS)	RX7	RX8
75 GHz	85.69%	23.45% (81.52%)	68.17%	86.08%
92 GHz	76.64%	26.95% (87.30%)	70.48%	87.38%
109 GHz	79.15%	34.71% (92.78%)	71.05%	80.94%

TABLE II
THE PAS SIMILARITY PERCENTAGE AT DIFFERENT FREQUENCY

Frequency	RX1	RX4	RX7	RX8
75 GHz VS 92 GHz	89.33%	86.03%	82.17%	81.72%
75 GHz VS 109 GHz	79.01%	78.67%	73.23%	68.14%
92 GHz VS 109 GHz	77.91%	79.49%	86.14%	80.64%

excluding LOS paths are marked. With the VAA scheme, a much better spatial resolution and improved SNR can be achieved for the PADP, leading to the “more specular” spectra.

A. Object consistency

Table I shows the PAS similarities at LOS and OLOS scenario at different locations. Note that only the LOS path of RX4 is obstructed. The similarities of RX4 are low since LOS path is dominant. To show the impact of LOS paths, the similarities after removing LOS paths are calculated (in parentheses) and generally a similarity above 80% can be observed, which indicates that paths in non-LOS directions are highly similar. These observations are valuable, since it means MPCs with presence of objects might be easily determined based on the shape and location of the objects and the MPC profiles without the presence of objects. Note that the presence of an obstacle object clearly generates a “shadow area”, proportional to its size and blocking all multipaths with angles of departure within a certain range. Moreover, the measurement results demonstrated that the object might also affect other paths in the propagation environment as well.

B. Frequency band consistency

The PADPs of different frequencies are shown in Fig. 3 and the similarities of PAS between different frequency bands at different locations for the LOS scenario are shown in Table II. The PAS similarity is generally above 70%, which can indicate that dominant MPCs are quite similar at different frequencies. Moreover, by carefully observing Fig. 3, we can see that some weak MPCs disappear or reappear at different frequencies. As the frequency goes up, the propagation channel tends to be more quasi-optical, leading to similar dominant propagation paths in the W-band. On the other hand, the transmission and diffraction loss will increase as the frequency increases, making the channel sparser and more specular. Some weak paths might disappear or reappear at different frequencies.

C. Spatial consistency

To better observe spatial consistency, the PADPs of different RX locations are superposed as shown in Fig. 4. However, classifying MPCs remains a difficult task. To better group the

Fig. 3. PADPs for LOS and OLOS scenario at different frequency from Rx4, and the paths in LOS direction are circled by white rectangles. (a) OLOS: 75-76 GHz. (b) OLOS: 92-93 GHz. (c) OLOS: 109-110 GHz. (d) LOS: 75-76 GHz (e) LOS: 92-93 GHz. (f) LOS: 109-110 GHz

MPCs at different Rx locations, we introduce a fitting curve which is calculated from the simple room geometry. The specular reflection is the main factor that accounts for generating most dominant MPCs except the LOS path. Combining the laws of specular reflection with the geometry of the room, mirror positions of RXs based on the propagation trajectory would be distributed on several straight lines and similar methods have been applied to estimate delay at different locations in street canyon scenarios [18]. Note that the fitting curve is valid for single-bounced MPCs as well as higher order bounces. Then, the expression for the fitting curve of MPCs in PADPs is

$$\tau = \frac{\tau_0}{\cos(\varphi - \varphi_0)} \quad (5)$$

where τ_0 and φ_0 denote the delay and azimuth of the nearest mirror point on the straight line, respectively. The points of most powerful paths are fitted by three red curves in Fig. 4. (A: $\tau_0 = 21$ ns, $\varphi_0 = 0$ deg; B: $\tau_0 = 28$ ns, $\varphi_0 = 0$ deg; C: $\tau_0 = 28$ ns, $\varphi_0 = 180$ deg). τ_0 and φ_0 of three curves correspond to the delay and azimuth of LOS, the first order reflection of LOS from the wall below and upper wall in Rx4, respectively. After obtaining fitting curves, grouping of paths can be determined by combining the continuity of RX location changes. MPCs of the same kind are continuous in PADPs over spatial locations.

Thanks to the continuity of MPCs of the same class as discussed, only the multipaths at RX1 and RX8 are displayed in Fig. 2 for demonstration. As shown in Fig. 4, some complete change trajectories, such as class “b”, “f” and “g”, correspond one-to-one to position changes of RX. The path of class “a” “d” and “e” are obstructed by the metal plate in the middle positions. The path of class “c” and “h” are incomplete due to the gap at stairs. We can clearly observe spatial evolution of

Fig. 4. The superimposition of PADPs at different location with fitted curves and classification of dominant MPCs.

the trajectory due to different locations, which can be exploited to predict spatial profiles from one location to another.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we performed analysis on the frequency, spatial and object consistency of channel parameters. The experimental results indicate that channel characteristics have good frequency consistency. Object in the LOS directions has almost no impact on non-LOS paths and channel characteristics have a strong correlation with the spatial environment. The above observations are of great significance for many applications, e.g. in fast beam alignment across frequency bands, different spatial locations or object changes. According to the spatial patterns of channel characteristics, dominant specular paths

over many spatial locations, with or without objects can be well predicted using simple map. In addition, though the measurement campaign was performed in relatively simple indoor environment, we have carefully designed the measurements to ensure that we can observe realistic propagation conditions among spatial locations. We believe the findings on frequency-, space, and object-consistency can be generalized to different indoor scenarios in principle. Further research is needed on the channel characteristics in more cluttered environments.

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